

were included (see table). Waxy and very low AC varieties always had soft GC, clearly indicated by the significantly negative correlation. The relationships between AC and GT, and GT and GC were not as perfect as that between AC and GC. □

Frequency distribution of AC, GT, and GC of rice group or subgroup. a = IRRI, b = Japan, c = Korea, d₁ = northern China, d₂ = southern China, d₃ = central China, d₄ = Taiwan. Thirteen of the 86 varieties were in d₃ from Hubei, China. AC type: ▨ = waxy (2%), ▩ = very low (2-11.9%), ▧ = low (12-19.9%), ▦ = intermediate (20-24.9%), ▥ = high (≥25%); GT type: ▨ = low (alkali spreading values 6-7), ▩ = intermediate (4-5), ▧ = intermediate to high (3), ▦ = high (1-2); GC type: ▨ = soft (gel length 61-99 mm), ▩ = medium (41-60 mm), ▧ = medium to hard (36-40 mm), ▦ = hard (≤35 mm).

Grain quality of F₁ hybrids between wide-compatible japonica rice 02428 and indica varieties

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We evaluated the grain quality of intersubspecies rice hybrids from the cross between six maternal indica varieties and wide-compatible paternal japonica rice 02428. Physicochemical characteristics were analyzed using standard methods.

The 1,000-grain weight of the six hybrids was 23.4-26.0 g, all within the range of their parents, except for Milyang

Physicochemical characters of indica-japonica rice hybrids at INAS, Hangzhou, China.

Variety or combination	1000-grain weight (g)	Hulling (%)	Length (mm)	L/W ratio	Chalkiness		Amylose content (%)	Gel consistency ^a (score 1-9)	Alkali digestion ^a (1-7)
					%	Score (0-9) ^a			
Shanyou 10 (check)	26.7	80.2	55	2.3	23.0	9	28.2	5	5
02428	24.2	79.7	44	1.6	50.0	9	18.5	5	3
IR1361	21.8	78.7	58	2.6	0.0	0	22.9	5	7
IR1361/02428	25.2	81.7	52	2.1	8.5	1	22.0	5	4
IR1362	22.3	80.6	51	2.1	0.5	0	21.9	9	7
IR1362/02428	23.4	81.6	51	2.0	5.5	1	17.2	1	4
IR1371	20.8	79.7	50	2.2	3.0	1	20.7	1	6
IR1371/02428	24.3	81.7	49	1.9	28.0	9	22.1	5	4
Milyang 46	25.6	80.4	54	2.3	2.0	1	21.3	9	6
Milyang 46/02428	26.0	82.4	51	2.0	11.5	5	16.9	9	5
Minghui 63	26.2	79.0	67	3.1	0.0	0	6.1	9	6
Minghui 63/02428	25.3	79.7	59	2.5	23.5	9	21.5	3	4
T64-7	22.5	78.5	67	3.5	12.5	5	28.4	9	3
T64-7/02428	23.5	81.1	57	2.3	5.0	1	28.3	1	3

^a Standard evaluation system for rice scale.

46/102428 (see table). None, however, exceeded the check Shanyou 10 (Zhenshan 97 A/Milyang 46). The hulling (brown rice) rate of most of the hybrids was higher than that of their parents and of the check combination, averaging 8.14%.

Grain length was between that of their corresponding parents, and usually more

similar to that of the longer grained parent. All hybrids showed some chalkiness, but were far less chalky than 02428.

Amylose content (AC) was 16.9-28.3%. AC of Minghui 63/102428 and IRI371/02428 exceeded that of their high parent whereas that of IRI361/02428 and Milyang 46/02428 was below that of

their low parents. None of the six hybrids displayed an obvious gel consistency pattern. Alkali digestion values averaged around 4.

The results indicate that the grain quality of the six intersubspecies hybrids was superior to that of the leading intrasubspecies combination Shanyou 10. □

Phenological and quality aspects of grains of rice *O. sativa* L.

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Environmental conditions influence the phenological and quality characteristics of rice grain. Lower ambient temperatures during rice growth shorten the germination and vegetative phase.

Lower temperatures during grain development tend to produce higher amylose content (AC) levels and lower values for gelatinization temperature (GT) of starch than at average temperatures.

Alkali spreading value and amylose content of commercial grain types under 2 ambient temperatures.^a

Grain type	Varieties (no.)	Alkali spreading value ^b (GT index)		Amylose content ^b (% db)	
		Temp A (21.9 °C)	Temp B (18.6 °C)	Temp A (21.9 °C)	Temp B (18.6 °C)
Medium	3	5.63 a	5.71 b	12.5 a	17.4 b
Long-wide	3	5.28 a	5.76 b	18.1 a	19.5 b
Short	2	6.42 a	6.51 b	16.2 a	17.5 b
Long-slender	17	5.20 a	5.62 b	22.7 a	23.1 b
GT LSD (0.05) = 0.13		AC LSD (0.05) = 0.91			
CV (%) = 3.06		CV (%) = 6.87			

^aA = normal temperature condition (21.9 °C), B = 30 d after October (18.6 °C). In the row, values with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

We studied the effect of ambient temperature on 25 rice varieties for 3 yr under two temperature conditions.

The experiment was laid out in a random block design with four replications in factorial 2 × 4 × 4. Alkali spreading value ranged from 2.5 in Century Patna 231 to 7 in IRGA409

(see table). AC ranged from 14% in Norin 20 to 27% in IRGA409. We divided the varieties into four sample groups based on their commercial grain types: medium, long-wide, short, long-slender. Under the two temperatures, the groups differed significantly in AC and GT (see table). □

Pest resistance—diseases

Reexamination of linkage relationships between blast (BI) resistance genes *Pi-i* and *Pi-z* using near-isogenic lines (NILs) of rice

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Pi-i and *Pi-z* are in the sixth linkage group on current linkage maps. *Pi-z* was reported to have linkage relations to marker genes *C*, *alk*, and *Lm (Se-1)*, all belonging to the sixth linkage group. The *Pi-i* locus was reported to be linked to the *Pi-z* locus, with a recombination value of about 30% in the repulsion phase. I found the loci independent of the other, based on F₂ segregation data using NILs, except for the BI resistance genes.

We have been developing NILs by repeatedly backcrossing the Japanese cultivar Nipponbare to different sources of resistance to the B1 fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara. The recurrent parent is a japonica cultivar susceptible to most of the B1 isolates collected in Japan. The NILs are similar to Nipponbare in height, maturity, and appearance. The pedigrees and resistance genes of NILs used in this

research are in Table 1. *Pi-z'* is a multiple allele of the *Pi-z* locus, which was introduced to a japonica line from an indica variety.

Seedlings of parental lines and F₂ plants were grown in a greenhouse. They were inoculated at the four- to five-leaf stage by spraying with an aqueous spore suspension of about 3 × 10⁵ conidia/ml. Isolates IBOS 1-1-1 and Ken 54-20 were used as the inoculum. They belong to the most common race in Japan, race 3.

Table 1. Pedigrees of NILs with BI resistance.

Line	Resistance gene	Pedigree ^a	Source of resistance	
			Cultivar	Origin
Kanto-IL 5	<i>Pi-z</i>	Nipponbare *3//Ou 287/2* Nipponbare	Zenith	USA
Kanto-IL 7	<i>Pi-i</i>	Nipponbare *3//Todorokiwase/2* Nipponbare	Todorokiwase	Japan
Kanto-IL 8	<i>Pi-z'</i>	Nipponbare *3//73-B205/2* Nipponbare	Morak Sepilai	Malaysia

^aOu 287 = Fukunishiki/Kiyonishiki Fukunishiki: 597/Zenith/597/3/Hatsunishiki. 73-B205 = Morak Sepilai/5 * Fujisaka 5.